

A Study of Pyrogallol Derivatives of Thorium

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Complex forming reactions of thorium with pyrogallol have been studied by potentiometric and preparative techniques. Equilibrium constants for the reactions:

have been found to be 4.786×10^{-7} and 5.035×10^{-8} respectively. Sodium and potassium compounds, $\text{M}_2[\text{Th}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}_3)_2] \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, have been isolated.

Potentiometric titrations of thorium nitrate with KOH in presence of pyrogallol show a sharp inflection at four equivalents of alkali per mole of thorium ion, indicating the possibility of an electrometric method for estimation of thorium.

In view of our recent publication¹ on catechol derivatives of thorium, it was considered of interest to extend similar studies to the thorium-pyrogallol system. Compared to catechol, pyrogallol has been found to be a stronger chelating agent for thorium ions. In addition to a mono derivative, pyrogallol forms a di derivative also.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thorium nitrate, $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, employed was of B.D.H. AnalaR reagent grade. Pyrogallol was a Merck product.

Thorium was estimated by precipitation with ammonium hydroxide and subsequent ignition to oxide after decomposing the compounds with aqua regia. Pyrogallol was estimated by oxidation² with ceric sulphate.

pH measurements were carried out with a Phillips pH meter (P. R. 9400), standardised against a 0.05M solution of potassium hydrogen phthalate. All the titrations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere at $32^\circ \pm 2^\circ$.

Reaction of Thorium Nitrate with KOH (4 to 5 moles) in presence of Pyrogallol (1 to 4 moles).—A thorium nitrate solution was treated with a KOH solution in presence of increasing molar concentration of pyrogallol. The precipitates so obtained were washed and dried in a vacuum desiccator for 24 hr. and analysed. The results are recorded in Table I.

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1. Agarwal and Mehrotra, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, **24**, 821.

2. Sharma and Mehrotra, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1955, **13**, 419.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	M/20-Th(NO ₃) ₄ .	M/4-Pgl.	1M-KOH.	Added ratio of Th(NO ₃) ₄ : Pgl: KOH.	%Th.	%Pgl.	Ratio of Pgl: Th.
1	20 ml	4 ml	4 ml	1 : 1 : 4	54.63	28.02	0.955
2	20	4	5	1 : 1 : 5	60.42	24.95	0.772
3	20	8	4	1 : 2 : 4	46.90	44.63	1.776
4	20	12	4	1 : 3 : 4	45.01	45.91	1.909
5	20	16	4	1 : 4 : 4	44.31	45.55	1.923

N.B. Pgl denotes pyrogallol.

Reaction of Thorium Nitrate with Caustic Alkalis (6 moles) in presence of Pyrogallol (molar ratio of pyrogallol to thorium nitrate=3:1).—The reaction mixture containing thorium nitrate (M/10, 40 ml, 0.004 g. mole) and pyrogallol (1.525 g., 0.012 g. mole) was treated with 1M-NaOH (24 ml, 0.024 g. mole) in nitrogen atmosphere. Anhydrous ethanol (100 ml) was then added when a white crystalline compound separated slowly from the reaction mixture. The compound was washed with ethanol and dried in a vacuum desiccator for 24 hr. The analysis corresponded to Na₂[Th(C₆H₃O₃)₂]. 7H₂O. (Found: Th, 35.25; Pgl, 37.50. Formula requires Th, 35.58; Pgl, 37.73%).

By a similar reaction with KOH, the compound K₂[Th(C₆H₃O₃)₂].7H₂O was obtained. (Found: Th, 32.52; Pgl, 36.40. Formula requires Th, 32.53; Pgl, 36.07%).

Electrometric Studies

Potentiometric titrations of thorium ions with pyrogallol (curves 1, 2, and 3 in Fig. 1) indicate chelation of the type:

The extent of lowering in pH of the system is a direct measure of the above type of chelation. A comparison with the corresponding catechol system¹ shows the greater extent of chelation with pyrogallol. Comparison of the curves (Fig. 1) also indicates that tendency for chelation increases with rise in pH of the system.

Curve 0 (Fig. 2) is similar to that obtained by Britton² for the potentiometric titration of thorium nitrate with NaOH. Curve 1 is throughout lower than curve 0 with a point of inflection at $m=4$ (where m represents moles of base added per mole of thorium ion). These facts together with the precipitation of the mono-pyrogallate derivative (Table I) indicate the following predominant reaction:

3. "Hydrogen Ions", Vol. II, Chapman & Hall Ltd., p. 60, 1956.

Curve 2 (Fig. 2) is again lower than curve 1, indicating further chelation. Inflection at four equivalents of alkali indicates the reaction:

Moles pyrogallol added.
FIG. 1

Curves 1-3 show titrations in presence of 0.2, and 4 moles KOH/Th⁴⁺ ion respectively.

m → FIG. 2.

Curves 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4 represent potentiometric titrations of 20 ml of 0.025M thorium nitrate with 1M-KOH in presence of 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4 moles of pyrogallol (0.25M) respectively; total volume of the initial reaction mixture=28 ml. m=moles of base added, per mole of thorium ion.

In alkaline medium the remaining two weakly acidic hydrogen atoms are also neutralised:

Formation of chelate (IV) has been confirmed by the actual isolation of its sodium and potassium salts.

The nature of the curves 3 and 4 (Fig. 2) is almost similar to that of 2 up to $m=5$. Lowering then, however, increases, probably due to presence of an excess of pyrogallol, one and two moles respectively. In these curves, inflections at $m=7$ and 8, respectively, correspond to the neutralisation of excess of pyrogallol (cf. Fig. 3) present in the system.

Titration of 4ml of 0.25M pyrogallol solution with 1M-KOH after addition of 24 ml of water in nitrogen atmosphere.

Titration of thorium nitrate with 0.1M-KOH in presence of pyrogallol in nitrogen atmosphere. Curve 1: $2.5 \times 10^{-3}M$ in thorium nitrate and $2.5 \times 10^{-3}M$ in pyrogallol. Curve 2: $2.5 \times 10^{-4}M$ in thorium nitrate and $1 \times 10^{-2}M$ in pyrogallol. Total volume of the initial reaction mixture = 50 ml; ionic strength = 0.1M- KNO_3 .

Equilibrium Constants

After establishing the reactions of thorium ions with pyrogallol, it was considered worthwhile to determine their equilibrium constants. In these studies, thorium nitrate ($2.5 \times 10^{-3}M$) was titrated with $0.1M$ -KOH in presence of pyrogallol (H_3A), using a medium containing potassium nitrate ($0.1M$) and low concentrations of the ligand and metal ions (Fig. 4).

Calculation of Equilibrium Constant of the Reaction for the Formation of 1:1 Complex

At the initial stage of titration curve 1 (Fig. 4), attempts were made to fit the data in equation:

The equilibrium constant, K_1 , for the above reaction is given by

$$K_1 = \frac{[ThA^+][H^+]^3}{[Th^{4+}][H_3A]} \quad \dots \quad (vi)$$

The values of pK_1 , calculated at various points on curve 1 (Fig. 4), are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

KOH (ml)	..	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0	1.2	1.6	2.0
pH	..	2.85	2.89	2.92	2.96	2.99	3.01	3.08	3.14
pK_1	..	6.32	6.33	6.31	6.32	6.30	*6.25	*6.18	*6.04

Mean value of $pK_1 = 6.318$ and $K_1 = 4.908 \times 10^{-7}$.

*Neglected.

Above a pH of about 3, there appeared a gradual fall in pK_1 values. This could be due to the hydrolytic effects in the system which may in short be represented as:

In these calculations, initial hydrolysis of thorium ions was left out of consideration. Taking into account the hydrolytic reactions:

and knowing the hydrolytic constants $K_{h_1} = 5 \times 10^{-5}$ and $K_{h_2} = 2.6 \times 10^{-5}$ for these equilibria, reported by Kraus and co-workers⁴, the final equation may be shown to be

$$\frac{10.4 \times 10^{-5}}{[H^+]^2} [Th^{4+}]^2 + \left\{ 3 + \frac{1 \times 10^{-4}}{[H^+]} \right\} [Th^{4+}] - 3 [Th^{4+}]_{total} - T_{OH} - [H^+] \} = 0 \quad \dots \quad (x)$$

(where T_{OH} represents the amount of alkali added).

From the above considerations, the value of the equilibrium constant was found to be 4.764×10^{-7} . In this case also, the relative constancy of the pK_1 values could be maintained up to a pH of about 3 only. Comparison of this value with that from Table II shows that

the above consideration does not affect the system to any appreciable extent. Although Sillen⁵ has indicated formation of even higher polymerised entities like $\text{Th}[(\text{OH})\text{Th}]_n^{n+4}$ at early stages of hydrolysis, the concentrations of these polynuclear complexes should be vanishingly smaller compared to the simpler hydrolytic products, $\text{Th}(\text{OH})^{3+}$ and $(\text{ThOH})_2^{6+}$, and would affect the system to a much lesser extent.

Calculation of Equilibrium Constant of the Reaction for the Formation of 1 : 2 Complex

$$\frac{[\text{ThA}^+][\text{H}^+]^3}{[\text{Th}^{4+}][\text{H}_3\text{A}]} = K_1 \quad (= 4.786 \times 10^{-7})$$

$$\frac{[\text{H}_2\text{ThA}_2][\text{H}^+]^4}{[\text{Th}^{4+}][\text{H}_3\text{A}]^2} = K_2$$

The amounts of various ionic species present in the equilibrium mixture may be calculated from the above equilibria and the relationships.

$$\frac{9.572 \times 10^{-7}}{[\text{H}^+]^3} [\text{Th}^{4+}]^2 - \left[4 + \frac{4.786 \times 10^{-7}}{[\text{H}^+]^3} \{ 2[\text{Th}^{4+}] \}_{\text{total}} + \right. \\ \left. [\text{H}_3\text{A}]_{\text{total}} - T_{\text{OH}} - [\text{H}^+] \right] [\text{Th}^{4+}] + 4[\text{Th}^{4+}]_{\text{total}} - T_{\text{OH}} - [\text{H}^+] = 0$$

The values of pK_2 , thus determined at various points on curve 2 (Fig. 4), are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

KOH (ml)	..	0.4	0.8	1.2	1.6	2.0	2.4	2.8
pH	..	2.67	2.71	2.75	2.80	2.85	2.89	2.94
pK_2	..	7.35	7.33	7.28	7.33	7.34	7.25	7.20

Mean value of $pK_2 = 7.298$ and $K_2 = 5.035 \times 10^{-8}$.

In an earlier publication¹, equilibrium constant for the reaction:

was calculated to be 2.98×10^{-5} , neglecting the initial hydrolysis of thorium ions. Applying the hydrolytic reactions (viii) and (ix) in this case also in a similar manner as described above, the value of the equilibrium constant was found to be $K = 2.70 \times 10^{-5}$. Comparison of this value with the earlier one ($K = 2.98 \times 10^{-5}$) shows that the hydrolytic effect does not affect the system to any appreciable extent.

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5: Sillen, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, 8, 299, 316; "Polynuclear Complexes Formed in the Hydrolysis of Metal Ions", p. 74, Proc. Symposium on Co-ordination Chemistry, Copenhagen, August, 1953.